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An Archival and Historical Survey of the Jewish Catacombs of the Villa Torlonia in Rome ¹

“Solo con un franco ed aperto incontro
e non facendo cadere nel silenzio i problemi di un oscuro passato,
si puo' contribuire a rimuovere diffidenze ed ostacoli,
riuscendo cosi' anche ... a creare una migliore e reciproca comprensione.”

H. Z. Gellar, “Il significato archeologico e storico
delle catacombe ebraiche di Roma,”²
Rassenga mensile di Israele, 44 (1978): 268-269.

1. The discovery of the catacombs in 1919 below the Villa Torlonia.

The catacombs discovered in November of 1919 during excavations to reinforce the foundation piers of the “*scuderie nuove*” or new stables at the southwest corner of the Villa Torlonia were the last to be identified as Jewish in Rome in modern times. Nearly a century later, they are still the most studied of Rome’s ancient Jewish cemeteries,³ although their accessibility has long been an issue for a variety of political, economic and environmental concerns.⁴ In light of the proposed changes to the Villa Torlonia,

¹ At present, the Torlonia catacombs (also known as the “Jewish catacombs” of the Villa Torlonia or via Nomentana) are considered to be in stable condition and are open to small groups of the public on occasion or by request to Rome’s Archaeological Superintendence, the government entity responsible for the site since 1988 (it had previously been maintained for much of the 20th century by the Vatican’s Pontifical Commission for Sacred Archaeology). There has not been enough government funding in recent years to support a regular schedule of visits, and the atmospheric conditions inside the catacombs could suffer with any dramatic increase of visitors to the site.

² “Only with a frank and open meeting, and not by leaving behind in silence the problems of a dark past, one can help remove barriers and mistrust, thereby succeeding ... also to create a better and reciprocal understanding.”

³ L. V. Rutgers, “Sul problema di come datare le catacombe ebraiche di Roma,” *BABesch* 81 (2006), p. 171.

⁴ The Torlonia catacombs are of particular interest to Rome’s Archaeological Superintendence because the land above them has been city-owned since 1978 and extensively developed since that time as a new cultural center for Rome. The three other Jewish catacombs in Rome that survive (Vigna Randanini, Vigna Cimarra, and the possible remains of those on the Monteverde), are subject to the same jurisdiction, but remain below private grounds. For recent conservation work and study inside the Villa Torlonia catacombs, see G. Caneva, G. Galottab, L. Cancellieria & V. Savoia, “Tree roots and damages in the Jewish catacombs of Villa Torlonia (Roma)” in *Journal of Cultural Heritage* 10.1 (January-March 2009), pp. 53-62; M. Barbera, M. Magnani Cianetti, F. De Cesaris, “Il piano di interventi per le Catacombe ebraiche di Villa Torlonia, la sicurezza strutturale tra le necessità conservative e la pratica di sorveglianza manutentiva,” in *Atti del VI Convegno Nazionale: Manutenzione e Recupero nella citta' storica*, ed. A. Centroni, Rome, 2008, pp. 310-327; M. Barbera & M. Magnani Cianetti, “Lo stato attuale de lle catacombe Torlonia” in *I beni culturali ebraici in Italia: situazione attuale, problemi, prospettive e progetti per il futuro*, ed. M. Perani, Ravenna, 2003, pp. 55-70; and F. de Cesaris, “Aspetti problematici degli interventi di consolidamento in siti archeologici: Terme Taurine a Civitavecchia e le catacombe ebraiche di Villa Torlonia” in *Conservare il passato: metodi ed esperienze di protezione e restauro nei siti*

including new structures that could directly affect the Jewish cemeteries and other ancient remains below its public grounds, we review the building history of the site and recent studies of the catacombs' chronology and conservation, with the expectation that what is known of these catacombs in their present state might undergo significant changes in the near future.⁵

Figure 1. Plan of the catacombs below the Villa Torlonia. M. Barbera & M. Magnani Cianetti, "Lo stato attuale delle catacombe Torlonia," in *I beni culturali ebraici in Italia: situazione attuale, problemi, prospettive e progetti per il futuro*, ed. M. Perani, Ravenna, 2003, p. 65, fig. 1.

At the time of the catacombs' discovery in 1919, the property of the *principi Torlonia* on the first mile of the via Nomentana was already distinguished by "fake ruins" and other 19th century tributes to the Antique, including semi-hypogaeal *nymphaea*, honorary columns, obelisks, a tribune, and even a modern cavern created along the lines of an Etruscan tomb.⁶ The family itself had sponsored some of the 19th century's most ambitious archaeological excavations around Rome at sites like Portus, Roma Vecchia,

archeologici, ed. C. Varagnoli, Rome, 2005 (not seen). New theories on the origins and growth of the Torlonia catacombs have been proposed by L. V. Rutgers, op. cit, n. 3, and "Radiocarbon Dates from the Jewish Catacombs of Rome," *Radiocarbon* 44:2 (2002), pp. 541-547. Rutgers has also evaluated demographic data from the Villa Torlonia catacombs in "Nuovi dati sulla demografia della comunità giudaica di Roma," *Hebraica hereditas: studi in onore di Cesare Colafemmina*, ed. G. Lacerenza, Naples, 2005, pp. 237-254 and "Reflections on the Demography of the Jewish Community of Ancient Rome," *Les cités de l'Italie tardo-antique: IV-VI siècle: institutions, économie, société, culture et religion*, ed. M. Ghilardi, C. J. Goddard & P. Porena, Rome, 2006, pp. 345-358. Surveys of the Jewish catacombs of Rome published over the last decade include L. V. Rutgers, "The Jews of Italy," *The Cambridge History of Judaism*, 4, ed. S. Katz, Cambridge, 2006, pp. 429-508; S. Cappelletti, *The Jewish Community of Rome from the Second Century BC to the Third Century CE*, Leiden, 2006; A. Hirschfeld, "An Overview of the Intellectual History of Catacomb Archaeology" in *Commemorating the Dead: Texts and Artifacts in Context*, ed. L. Brink & D. Green, Berlin, 2008, pp. 11-38; and, most recently, E. Laurenzi, *Le Catacombe Ebraiche di Roma. Gli ebrei di Roma e le loro tradizioni funerarie*, Rome, 2011, and C. Vismara, "Le catacombs juives de Rome" in *L'archéologie du judaïsme en France et en Europe*, eds. P. Salmona & L. Sigal, Paris, 2011 pp. 51-62.

⁵ In late February of 2011, at the press conference "Stati Generali di Roma Capitale," Rome's Mayor G. Alemanno announced that a proposed Holocaust Museum would include access to the Torlonia catacombs (L. Palmieri-Billig, "Italy's First Holocaust Museum to be built in Rome," *The Jerusalem Post*, February 22, 2011). The project itself has already been in the works for nearly a decade, and may still experience modifications and delays before its scheduled completion in 2013. In the meantime, back in 2005, the Italian government awarded euro 1,400,000.00 to restore and open the Torlonia catacombs to the public (P. Broghi, "Catacombe ebraiche: via al recupero," article in *Corriere della Sera* of July 27th, 2005, p. 5). Barbera, 2003, p. 64, states, however, that constant "vigilance" is necessary of any developments in proximity to the catacomb site.

⁶ G. Carretti designed most of the "fake ruins" on the Torlonia estate between 1832 and 1845: A. Agati, "Arredi del Parco," and "Una finta tomba etrusca," in *Villa Torlonia*, ed. A. Campitelli, Milan, 2006, pp. 165-182; also A. Campitelli, *Villa Torlonia. Storia ed Architettura*, Rome, 1989, pp. 11-12. Roman authorities were unaware of the "Etruscan Tomb" replica (mid-19th century) before recent work on the *Casino Nobile* brought this underground chamber to light.

and the Circus of Maxentius and Villa dei Quintillii on the Appian Way.⁷ A Torlonia palace in Trastevere housed many of the finds from these digs as well as items from other sites and collections.⁸ At least two sarcophagi on the Nomentana estate had been used for Jewish burials.⁹ Yet, until the 20th century, despite the fantastic (or, to some, “ridiculous”) display of imitation monuments and ruins in the villa grounds, surprisingly little was known about any genuine antiquities in the site, for the villa remained in private hands and was well concealed from the road.¹⁰ As a result, while major building work in

⁷ Alessandro Torlonia excavated in Porto (*fossa Traiana*) from 1863-1869. Epigraphic evidence of Jews in Porto is reviewed by D. Noy in *Jewish Inscriptions of Western Europe* 1, Cambridge, 1993, p. 30.

⁸ P. E. Visconti’s 1883 *Catalogue of the Torlonia Museum of Ancient Sculpture* lists the Torlonia family’s acquisitions over the course of the 19th century from the collections of the Giustiniani, Caitani-Ruspoli, and Albani, among others. According to Visconti, about 21 pieces of sculpture in the collection came from the Nomentana estate (A. Campitelli et al., *Villa Torlonia. L’Ultima Impresa del Mecenatismo Romano*, Rome, 1997, p. 329). On Alessandro Torlonia’s “heterogeneous” tastes, see also Campitelli, 2006.

⁹ These Jewish artifacts were not made public until the 20th century. The first example, a sarcophagus “a cassone” complete with its lid and decorated, as far as can be made out from the few images of the piece known to exist, with a menorah, ethrog, shofar, and lulab, was photographed by archaeologist R. Paribeni in the kitchen yard of the Villa Torlonia in 1919. Shortly thereafter, Fr. J-B. Frey identified a drawing of the same sarcophagus among the epigraphic notes of G. B. de Rossi (1822-1894), but located *circa* 1827 in what was then known as the “Palazzo Giraud,” a building in Rome’s Borgo district near the Vatican that was purchased by Torlonia in 1820 (bibliography in A. Konikoff, *Sarcophagi from the Jewish Catacombs of Ancient Rome: a catalogue raisonné*, 2d ed., Stuttgart, 1990, n. 13). According to de Rossi (ms. ICUR 41 f. 16216), the object was seen by G. Settele as an “urna grande di marmo di lavoro rosso.” A number of decorative items (specifically in mosaic) are known to have been transported from Palazzo Giraud to the Villa Torlonia, probably in the 1830’s after the family ceased to use the former as its primary residence in Rome (“Notizie degli lavori d’arte eseguiti nella Villa Torlonia fuori Porta Pia,” in Campitelli et al, 1997, p. 339). The piece is now missing: it was last seen during the first years of Mussolini’s residence on the Torlonia estate (1925-1943). The second sarcophagus, with the inscription JIWE 2.527, was first identified as Jewish by H. J. Leon in “An unpublished Jewish inscription at the Villa Torlonia in Rome,” *Jewish Quarterly Review*, n.s. 42 (1952), pp. 413-421. In contrast to the previous piece with its distinctly Jewish decoration, the front panel of this second sarcophagus is strigillated: only the faint inscription incised on the marble strip of the upper rim indicates its (secondary?) use by a Jew. In addition to these artifacts, G. Sacco, *Iscrizioni greche d’Italia: Porto*, Rome, 1984, pp. 104-105, n. 85, publishes an opisthographic fragment (JIWE 1.17) in the Museo Torlonia in Trastevere that mentions a *phrontistes* (with the curious note that it may not be an epitaph), but only this piece and one other believed to have come from the Torlonia excavations at Portus (Sacco, 1984, pp. 113-114, n. 93/JIWE 1.16), are likely to be Jewish. Sacco herself, on p. 51, accepts that the Greek inscriptions in the Museo Torlonia come from Portus, although documentation of individual pieces is lacking. The Torlonia were a devoutly Catholic family, but enjoyed close ties to the financial firm of Baron James de Rothschild, one of the strongest advocates during the mid-19th century for the Jews in Rome (before his death in 1868, de Rothschild had even considered purchasing the Vigna Randanini to protect the Jewish catacombs below its grounds). According to E. Pistoni, *Villa Torlonia e Mussolini*, Rome, 2009, p. 57, Prince Alessandro Torlonia, at one point, had considered draining the Tiber in order to retrieve ancient objects said to have been thrown into its depths during the fifth century CE invasions of Rome. Most famous among these rumored treasures is the candelabrum with seven branches taken from the Jerusalem Temple by the Roman emperor Vespasian in 70 CE. Roman Jews, on their part, very much hoped such a project would take place following the unification of Italy in 1870: F. Servi, “Cronaca Mensile Italiana” in *L’Educatore Israelita*, 11 (1873), pp. 116-117.

¹⁰ The English travel writer A. J. C. Hare dismissed the site as such and “not worth seeing” in his *Walks in Rome*, vol. 1, 4th ed., New York 1874, pp. 343-344 and it is found to contain “pigmy copies of ancient edifices, altogether out of taste” in Murray’s *A Handbook of Rome & Its Environs*, 14th ed., London, 1888, p. 491. Campitelli, 1997, p. 329, reproduces a note of 1828 that lists artifacts recovered during the excavation of a “lake” on the Torlonia grounds, unfortunately with no further information about the context

the Villa Torlonia is documented, few projects for the grounds have any clear record or explanation before the property's transformation into a city park in 1978.¹¹

Figure 2. Sarcophagus with Jewish objects in the Villa Torlonia kitchen gardens, ca. 1930. Now missing or destroyed. R. Paribeni, "Catacombe giudaiche sulla via Nomentana," *Notizie degli Scavi* 17 (1920), p. 155, fig. 2.

The original land purchase by Giovanni Torlonia in 1797 was of semi-rural terrain very close to the old city limits that had formerly been in the possession of the Pamphilj and Colonna.¹² The consolidation of these suburban properties by the via Nomentana had already begun in 1762 when Girolamo Colonna annexed the Lana Gardens and Vigna Abbati to his estate.¹³ Torlonia eventually bought this large, square plot by the road, and his son, Alessandro, nearly doubled its size again in 1828-1833 by purchasing the "Vigna

in which these items had been found (Campitelli, on p. 17, n.10, cannot even locate this lake on Valadier's plan). For the "catacomb" visible in the mid-19th century below the Torlonia estate, see below, n. 19.

¹¹ Campitelli et al, 1997, pp. 315-316, provides a brief description of the few remains of the "Fondo Torlonia" in the Central State Archives in Rome. R. Quintavalle, in *Alessandro Torlonia e la via Nomentana nell' Ottocento*, Rome, 2008, pp. 18-19, notes that until the late 19th century, many properties along the via Nomentana were used primarily as "vigne" or "cannetti" rather than as parkland for the wealthier estates. The smaller terrains were often leased "in enfiteusi" to those who actually worked the land. Most often, it was these tenants or their laborers who were responsible for the archaeological discoveries made in the course of planting or quarrying in these sites. A 1790 survey of the Colonna property, on the future Torlonia estate, lists orchards, gardens, and artichoke patches, with only a small part reserved for residential use; this, too, was of modest proportions (Campitelli, 1989, p. 12). The Jewish catacombs lay below this property, although extending in part below its boundary walls. Even so, a note of the rebuilding of these walls in the early 18th century makes no mention of the catacomb site (Campitelli et al, 1997, p. 8, n. 11).

¹² Campitelli, 2006, p. 11 and *ead.*, 1997, pp. 5-9. Cardinal Benedetto Pamphilj acquired this "Vignola" in 1673.

¹³ According to R. Quintavalle, 2008, pp. 19-23, the tracts by the roadside (illustrated in the 1748 Nolli plan of Rome) were the "Giardino Lana" (formerly belonging to the Giori and Brunetti families) and "Vigna Abbati," behind which the "Vigna (or Vignola) Panfilj" was found (another future acquisition by the Torlonia, the "Vigna Massimi," is also shown in Nolli's plan). The first three properties were merged by Cardinal Girolamo Colonna in 1762, and later sold by his heirs to Baron James de Marekenfeld. Giovanni Torlonia purchased the estate in 1797. According to Quintavalle, 2008, p. 25, pre-existing residences on the Pamphilj and Abbati properties were on the sites of Torlonia's "Palazzo Principale" and "Casino dei Principi". Valadier apparently modified yet another nondescript structure on the Pamphilj estate into the original (and quite monumental) "scuderie vecchie" (Quintavalle, 2008, p. 25 and Campitelli et al., 1997, pp. 157-163). At this time, the Torlonia catacombs would have extended below the villa boundaries into the neighboring "Vigna Massimi," with much of the actual site beneath the southwestern corner of the park behind the original stables of Valadier, as shown in the 1818 villa plan (Campitelli, 1989, p. 44, fig. 13). In 1842, Alessandro Torlonia (1800-1886) finalized the purchase of what was left of the nearby vigna Bolognetti from the noble Lucernari family, who had, in turn, purchased the site in 1812 from two Jewish merchants (Alatri and Modigliani). Torlonia, however, sold this particular property (not directly connected to his own residence) to the Patrizi family in 1863.

Pozzi” directly behind the estate.¹⁴ Only much later, in 1887, did Giovanni Torlonia’s granddaughter, the Princess Anna Maria, purchase the monumental “driveway” of the Massimi family that ran along the southwestern border of the Torlonia grounds.¹⁵ It was the acquisition of this narrow (70 m.) strip of land and country lane (soon re-aligned on its northwestern

corner at a right angle with the public road) that ultimately brought the Jewish catacombs to light.¹⁶

Figure 3. Vineyards in the Nolli plan of 1748. A. Frutaz, *Le piante di Roma*, 3, Rome, 1962, n. CLXIX.18 (t. 419).

Giuseppe Valadier’s extensive renovations to the property at the time of its acquisition by Giovanni Torlonia, and the modifications to the buildings and grounds carried out some decades later by Giovanni Battista Caretti, Quintiliano Raimondi, and Giuseppe Jappalli,

¹⁴ Campitelli, 2006, p. 15. This property, in the possession of Filippo Pozzi until 1828, is the “Vigna Celli” in G. Nolli’s 1748 plan of Rome. The dense, rectangular plots marked out on this site indicate its agricultural rather than exclusively residential use, as noted by Quintavalle, 2008, p. 18. At this time, in fact, it contained only a “casino di villeggiatura con stazzo” and wine cellar (Campitelli, 1989, p. 40). Torlonia would later dissolve all pre-existing rental contracts to obtain an exclusive use of the site, commissioning the architect G. Jappelli to re-design the grounds much along the lines of an “English garden”. An 1842 land survey of the area illustrates this substantial enlargement of the Torlonia estate (Quintavalle, 2008, p. 69), and Jappelli’s 1839 proposal for the gardens is reproduced in Campitelli et al, 1997, p. 45, fig. 14.

¹⁵ Princess Anna Maria Torlonia purchased the “vignolo Massimi” from the Massimi heirs in 1887 (Quintavalle, 2008, pp. 34-35). This may have been the site of the Marquis Angelo Massimi’s excavations in the early 18th century in proximity to the roadside (via Nomentana): R Lanciani, *Storia degli scavi di Roma e notizie intorno alle collezioni d’antichità*, 6, ed. P. Liverani & M. R. Russo, Rome, 2000, p. 61 (1719) & p. 117 (1733).

¹⁶ Quintavalle, 2008, pp. 35-36: the Torlonia stipulated at the time of purchase that their partner in the Massimi sale, the Maraini Company, must allow for the re-alignment of the road that crossed the property so that it could join with the main street (via Nomentana) at a right angle. Quintavalle notes that the small road, marked “vicolo che tende a Pratalata” on the Nolli plan, first splits off from the via Nomentana, and then divides into two separate routes, one running between the Lana and Pamphilj properties (blocked off in the 18th century by Cardinal Colonna); the other, dividing the estates of the Lana and Massimi. The latter tract became the modern via Lazzaro Spallanzani, and the former, via G. B. de Rossi, a modern street on a route that has linked the via Nomentana to the via Tiburtina since Roman times. At the close of the 1887 sale, the “Scuderie Vecchie” close to the new intersection, already greatly modified according to Caretti’s “neogothic” plan, were further enlarged with an “annex” by A. Carnevali (Quintavalle, 2008, p. 37).

preserved little, if anything, of the ancient structures in the site.¹⁷ Even work to enlarge the stables (*scuderie*) along the villa's southwestern border did not lead to the study of the nearby Jewish catacombs until decades later, in 1919, when an entirely new stable complex was built.¹⁸ Perhaps timing, in this case, was everything. Already in the mid-19th century, catacombs were seen below the Torlonia grounds, but they were treated as a distinctly minor feature, at best, a scenic piece.¹⁹ Yet just about the time these anonymous catacombs of the Villa Torlonia were being swallowed up by artificial hills and *laghetti*, efforts to modernize and enlarge the city brought other catacombs to light in practically every corner of suburban Rome.²⁰ While a number of these received close study and attention, far too many others disappeared or were drastically reduced in size once anything of value had been removed. For this reason, it is likely that had not the Villa Torlonia remained in private hands, even less would be seen of its Jewish catacombs today. In any event, thanks to the circumstances noted above, the catacombs in the Villa Torlonia attracted far more scholarly interest in the early 20th century than they would have had a century before, and a greater number of resources were also now available to support the study and preservation of these sites.

¹⁷ Preexisting structures on the Colonna grounds the time of their purchase by G. Torlonia in 1797 were the "casino centrale" of the former Vigna Panfili (heavily modified by Valadier, and later by Caretti) and a smaller residence in the former vigna Abbati, which became known as the "casino dei principipi". Quintavalle, 2008, p. 11 & p. 25, notes other earlier buildings or monuments (storerooms or sheds for farming, but also fountains and statuary) near the secondary roads or paths inside the site. G. B. Caretti modified and redecorated many of these structures, including the *scuderie vecchie*, between 1832-1840. At a slightly later date (*circa* 1842), Q. Raimondi constructed the "Limonaia" (Campitelli, 1989, pp. 37-39). Surveying the grounds during the mid-1980's, the archaeologist C. Vismara found a large number of ancient clay fragments above the catacomb site (including black glaze and sigillata pottery, amphorae, and clay lamps): C. Vismara, "I cimiteri ebraici a Roma," in *Societa' Romana ed impero tardoantico*, vol. 2, ed. A. Giardina, Rome/Bari, 1986, p. 367.

¹⁸ The *scuderie nuove* or "New Stables" for the "Villino Medievale" date from 1920 (Campitelli et al, 1997, p. 23). But a plan of the villa from the late 19th century in Quintavalle, 2008, p. 70, shows a small building on the land above the catacombs at the time of Torlonia's 1887 acquisition of the "vignolo Massimi", just behind the "Scuderie Vecchie". A 1900 map of the area published in Frutaz, vol. 3, 1962, n. CCXXI, t. 566, also shows a building in this location prior to the construction of the "Scuderie Nuove" in 1920. It is not identified, but Campitelli, 1997, pp. 156-157, raises the intriguing possibility that a "Chapel of St. Alexander" (possibly in honor of the early Christian martyr of that same name buried in another underground cemetery along the via Nomentana, and certainly a compliment to the chapel's founder, Alessandro Torlonia) had once stood on the site of the *scuderie nuove*, a location not perhaps entirely coincidental for a family chapel in "Neo-Gothic" style if it were known at the time that some catacombs lay below. The chapel had already disappeared by 1905, as it is not included in a buildings and grounds survey of that time. Its demolition, in fact, may date to the late 1880's, when Princess Anna Maria Torlonia had a bath complex within the Palace transformed into a private Christian shrine.

¹⁹ G. Checchetelli mentions his visit to a catacomb on the Torlonia estate in *Una giornata di osservazione nel Palazzo e nella Villa di S. E. il Sig. Principe D. Alessandro Torlonia*, Rome, 1842, quoted at length in Campitelli et al, 1997, appendix 5, p. 350. From the vague indications provided in Checchetelli's account, the catacomb appears to have been located below the former Vigna Pozzi, west of the original Pamphilj estate where the Jewish catacombs were later found, since some proximity is indicated to the neo-Gothic "Serra" and "Torre Moresca" as well as the "Grotte" destroyed in 1909. Contrary to popular belief (perpetuated even by Campitelli et al, 1997, p. 172), there is no evidence that this, too, is a Jewish site.

²⁰ G. Marchi, S. J.'s *Monumenti delle Arti Primitive Cristiani: Architettura*, published in 1844, dealt extensively with the Christian catacombs of St. Agnes and "Maius". Giovanni Battista de Rossi would also dedicate himself for over half a century to the study of the Roman catacombs, and play a deciding role in the identification of three other Jewish sites (Vigna Randanini, Vigna Cimarra and Vigna Apolloni).

Figure 4. The enlargement of the Torlonia estate from 1797 to 1887. Quintavalle, 2008, p. 70.

Yet the many rules and regulations of the new “Roma Capitale” did not necessarily allow easy access to an archaeological site. Rather, it would be the landowner himself, Prince Giovanni Torlonia, who would play the major role in deciding the Jewish catacombs’ fate. The greater part of the underground cemetery, including upper levels A-B-C,

lay below an undeveloped area between the “scuderie vecchie” and the greenhouse known as the “Limonaia”, but a few galleries of the lower site (D-E-F) extended into the grounds of the former “vignolo Massimi” annexed to the Villa Torlonia in 1887. As urban development was intensifying along the via Nomentana at this time, it was this less chaotic zone along the “viale Massimi,” the future via Lazzaro Spallanzani, that became a new pole of Torlonia building activity, a symbolic gesture, no doubt, of the family’s “rebirth” under Alessandro’s grandson, Giovanni, who had assumed control of the property upon his mother’s death in 1901.²¹ Very little, in fact, had been built on the Nomentana estate following Alessandro Torlonia’s long-delayed completion of the “Theatre” in 1874. Even now, in 1906, the construction of a new residence, the “Villino Medievale” in the vicinity of the Limonaia, would have been enough to signal the family’s historic presence in Rome. Yet Giovanni Torlonia may have viewed the excavation of catacombs below the “scuderie nuove” as yet another opportunity to

²¹ M. G. Massafa, “Villino Medievale” in Campitelli, 2006, p. 158 and Campitelli, 1989, pp. 17-18. Prince Giovanni Torlonia carried out construction of the “Villino Medievale” (1906-1907); rebuilding of the boundary walls (1910); renovation of the “scuderie” (1911); remodeling of the “Capanna Svizzera” into the “Casino delle Civette” (1908, 1913, and 1916-1919); and construction of the Gatekeeper’s Cottage (1920), “Scuderie Nuove” (1920), and “Villino Rosso” along the via Spallanzani (1922). A 1925 project to remodel the “Scuderie Vecchie” into office space, however, was never carried out (Campitelli, 1997, p. 159), no doubt because of the site’s new tenant, Benito Mussolini.

display his family's renewed power and prestige.²² The fact remains that it was he who entirely funded the excavation of the Jewish catacombs in 1919.²³

2. Antiquities on the first tract of the via Nomentana prior to the 20th century excavations.

A mons Judaeorum (Jewish cemetery) in a vigna beyond the “Porta Nomentana” is included in a bill of sale from 1264 for purchase by a convent nearby.²⁴ Given that the Torlonia catacombs were found already greatly damaged at the time of their discovery in 1919, it is not out of the question to see this as a reference to the Jewish cemetery in much earlier times.²⁵ Mention of Christian catacombs in the area is far more explicit. Throughout the early middle ages, the cemeteries of Nicomedes, St. Agnes, St. Emerentiana (Maius), and St. Alexander were fixed points on the itineraries to Rome's sacred shrines.²⁶ Travelers entering or leaving Rome through the “Porta S. Agnetis”

²² Quintavalle, 2008, pp. 34-37 and Campitelli, 2006, pp. 17-19. After the early 1920's, Giovanni Torlonia undertook no further building projects on his Nomentana property.

²³ R. Paribeni, “Catacomba giudaica sulla via Nomentana,” *Notizie degli Scavi d'Antichita'*, 17 (1920), p. 143. O. Marucchi, “Scoperta di un nuovo cimitero giudaico sulla via Nomentana,” in *Nuovo Bollettino di Archeologia Cristiana*, 26 (1920), pp. 57, concludes with a direct plea to Prince Torlonia to finance a complete excavation of the site.

²⁴ A. Berliner, in *Storia degli Ebrei di Roma*, trans. A. Audisio, Milan, 1992, pp. 81-82, quotes a document from July 4th, 1264, that mentions the “mons Judaeorum, il colle degli Ebrei” sul quale si trovava il “Campo (cimitero) dei Giudei” (Jewish cemetery). As no other distinctly “Jewish” artifacts have come to light on the via Nomentana (a sarcophagus with Latin inscription CIJ.1.72/JIWE 2.616, perhaps from the cemetery of St. Agnes, is recognized by some as Jewish, but on very little comparative grounds), the reference could well be to the Torlonia site. Berliner's study dates to the late 19th century, nearly three decades before the discovery of Jewish catacombs in the Villa Torlonia: consequently, he is somewhat at a loss to explain why the Jews would have used a site at such a great distance from their residences “across the Tiber” in Trastevere, where the Medieval “Campo degli Ebrei” or cemetery was found. Decades earlier, however, in 1865, G. B. de Rossi had already interpreted the phrase “de agger a proseucha” in CIL 6.9821 (JIWE 2.602) as evidence of a “possible” Jewish cemetery between the via Nomentana and via Tiburtina.

²⁵ M. Vitale, “Le catacombe di Villa Torlonia e di Vigna Randanini a Roma, la sinagoga di Ostia” in Perani, 2003, p. 49, calculates that about 100 tombs in the site (from a total of 3,828) are still sealed. In the millennium or so that followed the last burials in the Roman catacombs, while the general location and identity of many were still known, the Jewish catacombs became, at best, local landmarks that, like many other ancient ruins, provided a wealth of curious toponyms for areas outside of the city. The occasions when great damage was done to these sites cannot be fixed at any precise date. But for the frequent appearance of the menorah image, those who came across the Jewish cemeteries might even have assumed they were Christian, or tombs for “Greeks,” the language used in the majority of the Jewish inscriptions, unintelligible to the average Roman of later times. Because they may have contained relatively little stone and other materials for building purposes (in more modern times, they were considered quite “poor”), the Jewish cemeteries tended to suffer the same fate as that of the profane sites in Rome: they would be accessible for a short time while being stripped of their artifacts, and then reburied and soon forgotten. The exploration of underground cemeteries intensified during the seventeenth and eighteenth centuries in Rome, but so did endless debate over their origins as Christian burial grounds. Rome property owners, on the whole, found cultivation of the land above these sites more profitable (and far less problematic) than the exploration of what lay beneath. Open cavities leading into the catacombs were often the result of quarrying or landslides: small areas could also house animals or be converted into storage space.

²⁶ The ancient system of roads still operative during the early Middle Ages to link the Salaria, Nomentana, and Tiburtina up to the third mile is illustrated by V. Flocchi Nicolai, “Sacra Martyrum Loca Circuire:

(Porta Nomentana) would have passed close by the Torlonia site, but this does not appear to have been distinguished by any monumental “landmarks” above ground to attract a visitor’s attention.²⁷ It is also not known at which date its catacombs were first seen and pillaged. Tomb violation is readily apparent, yet there is no evidence of graffiti (the signatures of visitors) or other traces of modern access to the catacombs before 1919.²⁸

Antonio Bosio’s explorations of the catacombs of Rome around the year 1600 brought him to the via Nomentana on several occasions in search of Christian cemeteries.²⁹ In the centuries that followed, archaeological discoveries on both sides of the via Nomentana suggested that the Roman necropolis of the Salaria-Nomentana region had been used by Christians and, as it would later turn out, also by many Jews.³⁰ Despite these signs, Rome’s urban plan (Piano Regolatore) of 1883 determined that this area would house various government entities (including the Ministry of Transport and

percorsi di visita dei pellegrini nei santuari martiriali del suburbio romano” in *Christiana Loca: lo spazio cristiano nella Roma del primo millennio*, ed. L. Pani Ermini, Rome, 2000, pp. 221-230. Focchi Nicolai also stresses the importance of the via Nomentana well into the Middle Ages to access Christian sanctuaries and shrines in *I cimiteri paleocristiani del Lazio 2: Sabina*, Vatican City, 2009, p. 12. The Medieval indices and guides that mention the Nomentana cemeteries and shrines (particularly that of St. Agnes) are found in R. Valentini & G. Zucchetti, *Codice Topografico della città di Roma 2*, Rome, 1942, pp. 17-18; 78-79; 115; 144-145. Only those of Nicomedes are located on the right side of the via Nomentana (like the catacombs of the Villa Torlonia). Between the 7th and 9th centuries, many saints’ relics were translated from their tombs. In consequence, texts like the twelfth century *Mirabilia Urbis Romae* mention only the cemetery of St. Agnes and that of the “fountain of St. Peter” (Valentini & Zucchetti, 3, 1946, p. 27). The older Porta Nomentana in the Aurelian Walls (late third century CE) had been walled up by Bosio’s time (late 16th century) and replaced by Pope Pius IV with a new “Porta Pia” (1565). The project included the re-routing of the via Nomentana for a short tract as it left the city walls.

²⁷ Modern reconstructions of Ancient Rome in A. Frutaz, *Le Piante di Roma*, Rome, 1960, vol. 2, n. LI.1 (t. 102), n. LII (t. 110), n. LVIII (t. 118), indicate the original tract of the via Nomentana through this zone as well as the very few ancient structures known from literary sources. The recent topographical studies of U. Fusco, however, have not found any concrete archaeological evidence of these sanctuaries or shrines: Fusco, “Nomentana, via,” *Lexicon Topographicum Urbis Romae: Suburbium 4*, ed. A. La Regina, Rome, 2006, p. 98.

²⁸ A sarcophagus with a Jewish inscription (JIWE 2.554/CIJ 1.511) was found below the pavement of the church of S. Maria Antiqua in the Roman Forum, a site destroyed by natural causes in 847 CE. Until the mid-19th century, the provenance of this piece and many other epitaphs identified as Jewish in Rome is unknown. The scant number of epitaphs found in the Torlonia catacomb in 1919 and in 1973-74 could result from the thorough “harvesting” of its marble slabs in much earlier times, as was done in virtually every catacomb in and around Rome, be it pagan, Jewish, or Christian.

²⁹ The small catacomb and ruins of a mausoleum seen by Bosio in 1602 in the vigna of one “Pompilio Desideri” (*Roma Sotterranea*, 1632, p. 424; 435-436) are identified today as the anonymous cemetery of “via dei Villini”: see P. M. Barbini, “S. Nicomedis, coemeterium, ecclesia,” *Lexicon Topographicum Urbis Romae: Suburbium 4*, Rome 2006, pp. 94-95. Excavations in 1917, 1923, and 1938 on the site of the Ministry of the Railways (now Ministry of Transportation) came across tracts of a Christian catacomb on two levels in an area thought to correspond more closely to the location of the Nicomedes cemetery given by the Medieval itineraries (although found on the left side of the road, even prior to its modern alignment). This second catacomb was found in a very damaged state, with no artifacts *in situ*: only two arcosolia, “ad arco ribassato,” were seen in one gallery and, on the wall opposite, the entrances to two cubicoli.

³⁰ Fusco, 2006, pp. 96-113, identifies not only tombs (mausolea, columbaria, and burials “a cappuccina”) in this area, but also buildings for residential use (villas, cryptoportici, peristyles, baths, and fountains). P. M. Barbini, “L’area funeraria subdiale di Nicomede ed i rinvenimenti nella Villa Patrizi fuori Porta Nomentana,” *Domum Tuam Dilixi*, ed. P. Pergola, Studi d’Antichità Cristiane 53, Vatican City, 1998, pp. 15-16, believes that quite a large cemetery developed on both sides of the road, not only for Christian use.

Ministry of Public Works) as well as embassies, residences, religious institutions, and other structures for public and private use.³¹ The inevitable building craze that followed put at risk virtually all the area's archaeological remains.³² The Torlonia, on their part, invested heavily in the development of the properties surrounding their estate, villas that, like their own, had retained up to that time much of their rustic feel.³³

At long last, the time came for even the Torlonia estate to reveal some of the secrets of its past. The widening of the via Nomentana by about 40 meters in the first decade of the 20th century necessitated the demolition of Valadier's original entrance into the villa as well as that of a number of structures by the original road, including a 19th century "amphitheatre," "coffeehouse," and "Temple of Minerva."³⁴ Construction of the new traffic lanes and outer walls for the villa did, as a result, bring a number of ancient sepulchers to light, yet very little of these remained except for their foundations and "qualche avanzo d'ossa."³⁵ Something more was evident, however, in the catacombs also seen in the Villa Torlonia at this time: namely structural features like *cubicoli*, *lucernari*, and galleries with *loculi*, as well as examples of "tombe ad arcossolio ribassato", possibly a reference to the type known as "loculi ad arcossolio" in the catacombs later identified as Jewish in 1919.³⁶ Nothing is known of a Jewish or Christian presence in these sites. Even a wall in *opus reticulatum* and additional catacomb galleries below the via Lazzaro Spallanzani were given an "incerta attribuzione," perhaps

³¹ Cuccia, 2007, p. 27 and A. Campitelli, "Lottizzazione e distruzioni," *Le Ville a Roma. Architettura e giardini dal 1870 al 1930*, Rome, 1994, pp. 9-10.

³² Fusco, 2006, pp. 101-105. In 1914, Rome's National Museum acquired a marble funerary plaque with an inscription in Greek to an *archon*, accompanied by the symbol of the menorah (JIWE 2.532), believed – though not with certainty – to have come from the necropolis of the via Salaria and via Nomentana, possibly in the vicinity of the modern via Po.

³³ Quintavalle, 2008, pp. 9-16. Between 1845 and 1870, Torlonia steadily increased his holdings on the first tract of the via Nomentana, later selling off these properties in 1872 to the Banca Tiberina (subsequently absorbed into the Banca d'Italia and developed by the Societa' Generale Immobiliare).

³⁴ Quintavalle, 2008, pp. 38-39 and pp. 41-44.

³⁵ Fusco, 2006, p. 105.

³⁶ O. Marucchi briefly notes the discovery of catacombs in the Villa Torlonia in 1902 and 1903 in "Scoperta di gallerie cimiteriali sulla via Nomentana," *Nuovo Bullettino di Archeologia Cristiana* 7 (1902), p. 258 and "Gallerie cimiteriale sulla via Nomentana," *Nuovo Bullettino di Archeologia Cristiana*, 8-9 (1903), p. 285. According to a report by CDAS engineer Guglielmo Palombi, the first catacomb gallery brought to light in the Villa Torlonia on December 10th, 1902 during excavations to widen the via Nomentana was in an oblique position in regards to the road, and blocked after a short distance by dirt entering the site through a skylight or *lucernarium*. On its right wall were the entrances to two cubicoli, each nearly filled with dirt, but with tiers of arcossolia "ad arco ribassato" still visible. Another gallery branched off at left. As work on the trolley line continued, more catacombs emerged at the far end of the Torlonia property near the apartment complex at via Nomentana 234-235. A report again made by Palombi in collaboration with CDAS archaeological inspector Augusto Bevignani noted four galleries with loculi. A tile with a brick stamp from the local workshop SAI (Salaria region) was recovered from one partially sealed tomb. One gallery extended in the direction of the Villa Torlonia: the others terminated in the bedrock. Pressure to continue the Tramways construction and avoid any costly delays brought these investigations to an early close, and Marucchi observes to the effect that only time will tell if all the catacombs below the villa are connected. The PCAS (formerly CDAS) should still have on record Palombi and Bevignani's notes on the precise locations of these sites.

remaining anonymous because the land above them was now far too valuable to leave in the hands of the dead.³⁷

3. Excavations in the catacombs: 1919-1974.

The early 20th century discovery of Jewish catacombs was by all accounts accidental, but quickly turned archaeological with Prince Giovanni Torlonia's consent and financial support.³⁸ Italian archaeologist Roberto Paribeni, at that time involved with the excavation of Jewish catacombs on the Monteverde, carried out a partial exploration of the Torlonia catacombs between 1919-1920, in collaboration with technical engineer and site supervisor Agostino Valente and the architect Italo Gismondi.³⁹ The excavation was terminated, however, when part of the underground area threatened collapse, prompting the removal of a number of artifacts – including inscriptions – to storage rooms in the “Scuderie”.⁴⁰

In his 1920 report for the Italian government's archeological journal, *Notizie degli Scavi d'Antichità*, Paribeni defined the project as “provisional” since not all areas of the catacomb had been excavated, including those *sub divo* leading into the site.⁴¹ Yet, in retrospect, it is clear that he and his colleagues had seen a good deal of the 13,200 square

³⁷ Fusco, 2006, pp. 101-105. No connection has been established between these catacomb galleries and those in area F below the via Spallanzani (apparently never used for burial and now sealed). A number of mid-20th century plans in Frutaz, 3, 1960, document the area's archaeological remains, particularly the 1949 map of G. Lugli and I. Gismondi (the former employed by Torlonia to document the excavations at Porto: the latter responsible for the earliest map of the Villa Torlonia catacombs in 1919), which locates sepulchers and columbaria near the modern via Spallanzani (Frutaz, 3, n. LVIII, t. 118). Even less clear is the nature of a chamber and gallery accidentally discovered by a Torlonia servant: Pistoni, 2009, p. 97, is our only source for this “camera nel tufo della quale erano scavati rossi sedili,” found by the “Piccioniaia” in the vicinity of the “scuderie”.

³⁸ Paribeni, 1920, pp. 143-155. A. Hirschfeld, 2008, p. 33-35, rightly finds that “the exploration of the Roman Jewish catacombs has often been closely tied to the efforts of the individuals who owned the land under which the catacombs were found (e.g., the Randanini and Princes of Torlonia).” Only very recently has the Italian government allocated funds to properly restore these sites.

³⁹ R. Paribeni, “Iscrizioni del cimitero giudaico di Monteverde,” *Notizie degli Scavi d'Antichità* 16 (1919), pp. 60–70 and “Iscrizione latina del sepolcreto giudaico di Monteverde sulla via Portuense,” *Notizie degli Scavi d'Antichità* 20 (1921), pp. 358–360. In addition to his 1919 article on the Nomentana catacombs, Paribeni briefly mentioned the Torlonia catacombs in “Culti e religioni in Roma imperiale secondo recenti scoperte archeologiche,” *Atene e Roma*, n.s., 1 (1920), pp. 181-183. Another early article focusing on the inscriptions from the Torlonia site is that of B. Manna, “L'epigrafia del cimitero giudaico di via Nomentana,” *Bullettino della Commissione Archeologica Comunale di Roma* 48 (1922), pp. 205-225. The Commission for Sacred Archaeology first inspected the site in 1919, but took no active role in the privately sponsored excavation: Marucchi, 1920, pp. 55-57 and *Le Catacombe Romane*, Rome, 1932, p. 681.

⁴⁰ Paribeni, 1920, p. 143, blames tomb-robbers for the catacomb's damaged state, particularly in area A, the upper region that conserves richly decorated chambers and arcosolia but virtually no inscriptions. H. J. Leon's 1927 Harvard Ph.D. thesis, *De Judaeorum antiquorum sepulcretis Romae repertis quaestiones selectae tratavit*, identifies the inscriptions seen by the early 1920's in storage in the *Scuderie*.

⁴¹ Gismondi's plan in Paribeni, 1920, p. 144. The catacomb would have required extensive restoration before excavations could continue, and Prince Torlonia was no doubt more concerned with the expenses of his new garage. Leon, 1928, p. 313, notes that it had been necessary to “buttress the vaulting of many galleries with wooden supports”. Pistoni, 2009, p. 96, recalls that there were three depressions in the area surrounded by wooden fences during Paribeni's excavation. One hole later remained to provide access to the catacombs: all the others were filled in.

meters of underground space, even if much still remained cluttered with debris.⁴² Paribeni was the first to correctly identify the two separate excavations that had joined at a single point: where gallery C1 breaks into the upper part of E1.⁴³ More importantly, he could also establish a Jewish presence in the site (initially presumed Christian) from the dozens of partially preserved epitaphs to Jewish men, women and children (a few fragments of marble sarcophagi were seen as pagan in origin, and a Christian monogram was visible on at least one clay lamp in the site, but “mixed” finds such as these were not uncommon in excavations around Rome).⁴⁴ The catacomb itself did not appear to extend far beyond the public roads surrounding the property. One of the original entrances, that still used today, is close to the via Lazzaro Spallanzani: the other, with a similar

orientation but located well within the villa grounds, was uncovered in 1973 but subsequently reburied.⁴⁵

Figure 5: painting of a ceiling vault (cubiculum A). J-B. Frey, C.S. Sp., *Corpus Inscriptionum Judaicarum* 1, Vatican City, 1936, p. CXXVII.

The experience was no doubt a far more pleasant one for Paribeni than that of leading recovery operations inside the catacombs on the Monteverde already blasted apart by dynamite and now all but impossible to save.⁴⁶ And it did seem at first that the Torlonia estate would hold its ancient heritage more peacefully below a private lawn. In the years immediately following the discovery, Prince Giovanni Torlonia readily granted access to the site to Jewish, Protestant, and Catholic scholars.⁴⁷ The explorations of the young American classicist H. J. Leon (1922), the German scholars H. Lietzmann and H. W. Beyer (1925), and Fr. J-B. Frey of the Pontificium Institutum Biblicum in Rome (1928) all produced in-depth studies of the Jewish catacombs at this time.⁴⁸ Further steps for their preservation

⁴² Paribeni, 1920, p. 154, estimates the number of tombs as 4,500, distributed over an estimated 900 meters of gallery space below 2 hectares of terrain.

⁴³ Paribeni, 1920, pp. 143-155, finds this connection of E1 and C1 “contra volunta”, i.e., unplanned.

⁴⁴ Leon (1928, p. 113) and Frey (CIJ 1) both count 68 inscriptions in the site. Many sarcophagi fragments are described in Leon, 1960, pp. 215-216, n. 1, as well as a lamp with Christian monogram, p. 225.

⁴⁵ Paribeni, 1920, p. 144: “E’ da notarsi che le gallerie sinora scavate s’arrestano prima di giungere sotto l’attuale via Nomentana e via Lazzaro Spallanzani, contenendosi dunque tutte in terreno privato e non invadendo il sottosuolo del terreno pubblico (the ancient Roman road).” It would appear, therefore, that instead of increasing the cemetery area from above, the original excavators had preferred to enlarge what already lay below, leaving entry to the site restricted to just two points of access.

⁴⁶ R. Paribeni, 1920, 143-155.

⁴⁷ Frey visited the site three times in 1928 (Noy, 1995, p. 341).

⁴⁸ H. Gressmann, “Jewish Life in Ancient Rome” in *Jewish Studies in Memory of Israel Abrahams*, New York, 1927, pp. 170-191; E. Loevinson, *Roma Israelitica: Wanderungen eines Juden durch die Kunststaetten Roms*, Frankfurt on the Main, 1927; H. J. Leon, “The Jewish Catacombs and Inscriptions of Rome: an account of their discovery and subsequent history” in *Hebrew Union College Annual*, 5 (1928), pp. 299-313; H. W. Beyer & H. Lietzmann, *Die Judische Katakombe der Villa Torlonia in Rom*, Berlin-Leipzig, 1930; J-B. Frey, *Corpus Inscriptionum Judaicarum* 1, Vatican City, 1936, pp. 9-46, nn. 6-71.

were taken in 1929 when the Lateran Treaty placed the Torlonia catacombs in the care of the Holy See together with the other Jewish and so-called “heretical” catacombs of Rome.⁴⁹ Ironically enough, the site itself was already inaccessible, and would remain so for nearly two decades due to the arrival of a new neighbor, the Fascist dictator Benito Mussolini, who “rented” the Torlonia estate, it was said, for the token sum of 1 lira while Torlonia himself retired to another house on the property, the “Casina delle Civette,” until his death in 1938.⁵⁰ During Mussolini’s residency from 1925 to 1943, a number of the villa’s subterranean structures were incorporated into air raid shelters for Il Duce and his family.⁵¹ While the Jewish catacombs were never violated in this manner, they were nonetheless kept under close watch, as it was feared that Allied forces might use these pre-existing (and well documented) galleries as the means by which to enter the grounds undetected.⁵² The Villa Torlonia remained occupied at war’s end, but this time by victorious British and American troops, who did not evacuate the premises until 1947.

The Pontifical Commission for Sacred Archaeology (PCAS) carried out emergency repairs to the catacombs in 1946 following reports of their profanation by English troops.⁵³ In later decades, however, far more activity went on in the Roman law courts than in the site itself. While the fate of the Villa Torlonia still hung in the balance, most of its buildings were either abandoned or reduced to administrative use.⁵⁴ The land above the catacombs came very close to being divided up into building lots at this time, but, at long last, Rome got her way and salvaged the Villa Torlonia as a public park.⁵⁵

⁴⁹ The “heretical catacombs and Jewish catacombs of Rome” had already been placed in the care of the Commission for Sacred Archaeology through a “special convention” in 1912: *Acta Apostolicae Sedis: commentarium officiale*, vol. 9, pars 2, 1917, p. 626.

⁵⁰ By the early 1930’s, G. De Angelis d’Ossat was unable to conduct a geological survey on the property for the first volume of his series, *Geologia delle Catacombe Romane*, Rome, 1938, p. 267 & p. 286.

⁵¹ Pistoni, 2009, pp. 12-15.

⁵² Barbera, 2003, p. 63 & Campitelli, 2006, pp. 184-187, locate the bunkers built for Mussolini below the property. Contrary to what is often stated, the Torlonia catacombs never served this purpose, although those in the Vigna Randanini were among the underground sites used as bomb shelters during World War II. U. M. Fasola, “Consegna della catacomba ebraica di vigna Randanini alla Soprintendenza Archeologica di Roma,” *L’Osservatore Romano*, June 13th, 1986, p. 3, clarifies: “Gli interventi della PCAS per la conservazione e la valorizzazione delle catacombe ebraiche si sono potuti esplicare fin della scoperta a Vigna Randanini, mentre per quella di Villa Torlonia, scoperta nel 1919 in situazioni particolari, ben presto aggravate dall’occupazione del luogo da parte di Mussolini, li hanno rimandati negli ultimi decenni. In compenso questo monumento non ha sofferto i gravi danni operati a Vigna Randanini, come in molte altre catacombe cristiane di Roma, dalla loro utilizzazione come rifugi antiaerei durante la guerra e luoghi di nascondimento per ebrei e militari sbandati negli anni dell’occupazione nazista.”

⁵³ Leon, 1960, p. 63 (who returned to the site in the early 1950’s). Pistoni, 2009, pp. 96-97, reveals that the English soldiers, “to see what was inside, liberated the blocked entranceway (of the catacomb) and brought up ... many bones that, because of their age, soon turned to dust.” In light of this and other reports of the “sacking” of the Villa Torlonia by Allied Troops, the entrance E to the catacomb was secured in 1946. Valadier’s original *scuderie vecchie* were demolished shortly thereafter, in 1948. (Campitelli et al., 1997, p. 163).

⁵⁴ G. Tomassetti, *La campagna romana antica, medioevale e moderna: Vie Nomentana e Salaria, Portuense, Tiburtina*, ed. L. Chiumenti & F. Bilancia, 1979, p. 110 and Campitelli, 2006, pp. 17-20 & pp. 37-39 (discovery of panels buried on the grounds). Giovanni Torlonia, Jr. had died without direct issue, but distant relatives of the Torlonia, the Gerini, Cesarini, and Sforza families, repeatedly sought to annul Rome’s order to expropriate the villa for use as a public park. During this time, the Villa Torlonia was left in a severe state of disrepair with many of its decorative elements demolished or removed from the site.

⁵⁵ I. De Tuddo, “Le catacombe ebraiche,” *Capitolium*, 47.2-3 (1972), p. 41.

Shortly after proceedings for the Villa's expropriation to the city began in 1972, the PCAS carried out a new survey of the Torlonia catacombs in order to thoroughly clean out and restore the site.⁵⁶

The digging and repair work between November of 1973 and June of 1974 left the two catacombs fully accessible and in stable condition.⁵⁷ In addition, once the peripheral areas and original pavement level of virtually all the galleries had been exposed, excavations director Fr. U. M. Fasola was able to identify many elements of the catacomb's topographical development as well as some 25 inscriptions newly recovered from the site.⁵⁸

⁵⁶ This was part of an ambitious PCAS program to document and restore all the catacombs in Rome. In this same period, in the early 1970's, the Jewish catacombs of the Vigna Randanini were also being restored: D. Mazzoleni, "Le catacombe ebraiche," *Studi Romani*, 23.3 (1975), p. 295. The PCAS *Giornali di Scavo*, 12-13 (1972-1974), note work in progress on the Torlonia site, including the discovery of many artifacts later photographed for Fasola's article in 1976 (Fasola's own notes are in a private collection). Barbera, 2003, p. 60, finds that the areas where the PCAS built new walls for reinforcement (particularly in A2) exist, on the whole, below structures above the site, or where the terrain has otherwise been greatly disturbed.

⁵⁷ U. M. Fasola, "Le due catacombe ebraiche di Villa Torlonia," *Rivista di Archeologia Cristiana* 52 (1976), pp. 7-62. F. Zevi, p. 169, labels the PCAS restorations (the brick supporting piers) "massicci e snaturanti" but agrees they have contributed towards a complete accessibility of the site, especially between areas C and E. Rutgers, 2005, p. 246, also notes the "scrupulous care" with which the PCAS had marked each loculus behind the modern piers.

⁵⁸ Fasola, in fact, stressed that the catacomb had developed as two separate excavations, calling the lower catacomb (particularly area D) "la cataomba delle epigrafi" and the upper one (areas A-B-C) that "delle pitture": Mazzoleni, 1975, pp. 300-301. Documented for the first time in Fasola's work are galleries on the very periphery of the upper and lower catacombs: area F (probably an abandoned water conduit, connected to the lower catacomb D but apparently never used for burial); gallery C1 (terminus at north); C3; A8 (terminus at northeast); A1 (terminus at northeast); and A6-A7 at the extreme eastern edge of the site. The lower chamber of the "double cubiculum" Ab-c in A2 was also revealed at this time. While Fasola completely cleaned the catacomb, in the sense that every tomb was now visible down to the original floor level in the galleries (with the exception of *formae* tombs), he did not publish any stratigraphic data from the Torlonia site. Arcosolium A6 now displays lamps and other artifacts recovered in his dig, and the arrangement of inscriptions in the site is also largely modern. A small number of Jewish artifacts from the Villa Torlonia was taken to the PCAS study collection: C. Salviati, "Il catalogo degli oggetti minuti conservati presso la PCAS," *Rivista di Archeologia Cristiana*, 54 (1978), pp. 106-107 & n. 1, fig. 56. A new inventory is now being taken of these finds (Laurenzi 2011, p. 63 n. 86). Among the excavation notes of February 22d, 1974 is the drawing of a metal object (3.4 cm, in circumference, 55oz in weight) from area A, embellished with a Greek cross, palm branches, and some letters (γ? ρ?): PCAS *Giornale di Scavo*, 13 (1974), pp. 66-67. This may indicate continued access to the site well into medieval times.

Figure 6. Drawings of the artifacts recovered from the Torlonia catacombs (area A6) on February 21-22, 1974, PCAS *Giornale di Scavo*, 13 (1974), pp. 66-67.

Following another official inspection in 1977 at the time of the Villa Torlonia’s expropriation by the city of Rome, the PCAS “backfilled” the entrance into area E by the via Lazzaro Spallanzani to safeguard the site in an area still much neglected and in serious disrepair.⁵⁹

The mid-1970’s also marks the time of historic talks between the Roman Catholic Church and Italian state to re-ratify the 1929 Lateran Treaty.⁶⁰ Jewish groups successfully lobbied both the Church and Italian State at this time to hand over the care of the Jewish catacombs to Italy.⁶¹ Amid noted polemic about the Jewish catacombs’

⁵⁹ Tommasetti, 1979, p. 113. An article by Pietro Bottali, “Catacombe: ci sono anche quelle ebreo” appeared in the Roman daily *Il Messaggero*, August 29th, 1977. H. Z. Geller also described the situation in “Il significato archeologico e storico delle catacombe ebraiche di Roma” in *La rassegna mensile di Israel*, 44 (1978), pp. 268-282. On his part, Fasola, 1986, p. 3, explains the reasons for reburying the entrance to the Torlonia site: “... Come si e’ accennato, la consegna della Catacomba di Villa Torlonia, il cui ingresso e’ al presente interrato per ragioni di sicurezza, e’ stato rinviato d’accordo con il Ministero per i Beni Culturali, essa avverra’ non appena dalle competenti autorità saranno stati attuati i presupposti tecnici indispensabili.” Fasola also notes that attempts had already been made to force the modern entry into area E, and acts of vandalism and theft were rampant in many other areas of the park. These crimes are also mentioned in Campitelli et al., 1997, p. 138, n. 218; p. 155 and p. 205.

⁶⁰ M. Vitale, 2003, p. 47, calls the 1974 Congress of the Unione Comunità Israelitiche Italiane the “modern birth” of Jewish catacomb history in Rome.

⁶¹ According to the article, “New Light on the Jewish Catacombs” published by *Time Magazine* on May 23d, 1977, both the United Italian Jewish Communities and the World Jewish Congress gave high priority in 1977 to creating “guidelines aimed at constructive collaboration between the responsible Italian

“suppression,” “abandon,” and need for “de-Vaticanification” (in hopes that the ancient Jewish funerary artifacts also in the Vatican’s possession would also be handed over to the Jews of Rome), article 12.2 of the new Concordat of February 15th, 1984 ratified Italy’s sole responsibility for the maintenance and conservation of the ancient Jewish sites.⁶² Rome, herself, had great plans for the Villa Torlonia, but was slow to act on her words, thereby delaying the official concession of the Torlonia catacombs to the secular government for a number of years, until 1988.⁶³ The following year, in 1989, Rome’s Archaeological Superintendence began collaborating with the Unione delle Comunità Ebraiche in Italia (UCEI) for the maintenance and conservation of the surviving Jewish cemetery sites.⁶⁴

authorities and the Jewish world for the purpose of safeguarding, preserving, and exploring the Jewish catacombs in Italy and making them accessible to scientific research and to the public.”

⁶² M. Vitale, 2003, pp. 47-48. H. Z. Gellar, 1978, pp. 281-282, quotes at length the discourse of former Fine Arts Minister G. Spadolini in *La Voce Repubblicana* of January 15th, 1977, where the liberal politician alleges a “grave stato di degradazione e di abbandono” of the Jewish catacombs, and how, in light of rising anti-Semitism, their tutelage would be a “test decisivo” for the Italian State. A number of international reporters interpreted the polemic as a sign that the Church was unwilling to concede its authority over these sites to the Jews: M. Ledeen, “The Unknown Catacombs,” *Commentary Magazine* (1977), pp. 64-66, and letters in response to Ledeen’s article in the magazine’s November 1977 and January 1978 issues; Tullia Zevi and Sam Waagenaar, “The Jewish Catacombs of Rome: A Neglected Treasure of Our Past,” *Hadassah Magazine*, December, 1979, pp. 12-12 & pp. 38-39; and L. Pitigliani, “A Rare Look at the Jewish Catacombs of Rome,” *Biblical Archaeology Review*, 6 (1980), pp. 32-43. While Zevi and Elio Toaff, then Chief Rabbi of Rome, display a thorough knowledge of the situation (Zevi is correct to label current scholarship as less than explicit on the development of Jewish and Christian catacombs in Rome), and recognize, on the whole, the Vatican’s critical role in the preservation of the Jewish catacombs during much of the 20th century (along with dozens of Christian and private sites), others, particularly members of what Fasola terms the “misinformed press” reveal, if anything, their great ignorance of the Jewish catacombs, having little or no idea of their extent, contents, time of use, and the conditions during which they were discovered and excavated in modern times (legally regarded as “profane” monuments, the Jewish catacombs until 1929 were not subject to the laws protecting many of the Christian cemeteries). Charges that the Vatican was “hiding” explosive evidence, deliberately preventing access to the site, and hoarding Jewish artifacts in its churches and museums were either not true or presented very inaccurately (while some very good points can be made about whether or not the Roman Curia should have ended up with nearly every inscription from the Monteverde site, the majority of inscriptions from the Torlonia and Randanini catacombs remain *in situ*). In addition, some comments of Fasola to the Italian press are quoted by reporters like Ledeen, 1977, pp. 64-66, without identifying Fasola’s actual concerns (namely, that the Italian State had had a very poor track record of preserving funerary hypogaea in Rome, and the Archaeological Superintendence itself was continuing to display little interest in documenting these burial sites without PCAS intervention and expertise). The PCAS nevertheless continued to dialogue with the Superintendence in even these most difficult times: E. Della Riccia, “Le catacombe ebraiche sotto la Villa Torlonia,” *Strenna dei Romanisti* 45 (1984), pp. 137-138.

⁶³ Vitale, 2003, pp. 48-49, n. 2 and Barbera, 2003, p. 63. In the late 1980’s, S. A. Dayan compiled an inventory of about 480 artifacts in the Torlonia site that she dated from the late second through late fifth centuries CE, including 90 epitaphs and a number of sarcophagi fragments and objects in metal and clay.

⁶⁴ This was ratified on March 8th, 1989 (101 art. 16 in “Norme per la Regolazione dei Rapporti tra lo Stato e l’Unione delle Comunità Ebraiche in Italia”). M. R. Barbera, 2003, p. 55, notes that the initial work carried out by the Soprintendenza Archeologica di Roma in the late 1980’s with a budget of 450,000,000 lire was to unearth the entrance into the catacomb that is currently in use and install essential electrical and alarm systems inside the site. Additional details about this “transitional phase” are found in F. Isman, “Un tesoro nascosto: le catacombe ebraiche. Un incontro con Tullia Zevi,” *Archeo*, 91 (1992), pp. 108-117. Zevi, the first female president of the UCEI from 1983-1998, long sought to publicize the ancient Jewish sites in Rome with better signage and regular opening hours.

A flurry of activity has gone on inside the Torlonia catacombs since this time. While restoration work in 1994 prevented D. Noy from conducting a survey *in situ* of the Jewish epitaphs for the second volume of *Jewish Inscriptions of Western Europe* (1995), a grant from the World Monuments Fund the following year funded studies of public access to the site.⁶⁵ An independent project in 1997 by researchers from the University of Utrecht analyzed the radiocarbon dating of organic matter from the tombs.⁶⁶ Additional measurements carried out by the Archaeological Superintendence between 1998 and 2001 with the use of georadar and electromagnetic waves have also revealed new details of the catacombs' location and extent.⁶⁷

By the early 1990's, restoration work had also begun in other areas of the Villa Torlonia, including the monumental "Casino Nobile" and "Scuderie" not far from the Jewish site.⁶⁸ The city's promise is to "return the Villa Torlonia to her ancient glory" while conceding space and funding to modern amenities for public use (as in the case of the "scuderie nuove", now a senior center). But with multiple government agencies involved in the villa's upkeep, some recent proposals and studies appear to put the catacombs at risk, or simply ignore their existence altogether.⁶⁹ At this time this article goes to press (2012), the process to "streamline" operations in the villa has only just begun.

⁶⁵ Noy, 1995, p. 341. The Villa Torlonia epitaphs are nn. 410-529 in *JiWE* 2. In 1994-1995, the World Monument Fund's "Jewish Heritage Program" and the Samuel H. Kress Foundation sponsored the efforts of an international team of scholars led by the architect G. Torraca to create a preservation program for the Jewish catacombs of Rome in the hopes of re-opening the Torlonia site to the public by the Jubilee Year of 2000: Barbera, 2003, p. 56, n. 2, and G. Torraca, *Catacombe ebraiche nella Villa Torlonia, report to the Rome ICCROM and World Monuments Fund in New York* (not seen).

⁶⁶ A team of researchers led by prof. L. V. Rutgers from the University of Utrecht surveyed the Torlonia tombs in June-July of 1997: Barbera, 2003, p. 63. The results of this study have been published in a number of scientific journals and conference proceedings: see n. 4 and the bibliography at the end of this paper.

⁶⁷ Barbera, 2003, p. 56 and Cappelletti, 2006, p. 165: only the skylight in front of arcosolium A6 was opened. According to Mazzoleni, 1975, p. 295, there are four other skylights in areas D-E.

⁶⁸ The 2000 "Roma Capitale" campaign (Legge 396/90) included the following projects for the Torlonia site: 227, b3.1.1.1, "Restauro e ristrutturazione degli edifici monumentali all'interno di Villa Torlonia," 4/7/94, 15,540,358.38 (completed); 228, b3.1.1.1, "Ristrutturazione degli edifici monumentali e delle catacombe all'interno di Villa Torlonia," December 21st 2000, 1,389,197.73 (completed); 229, b3.1.1.2, "Restauro da parte della Soprintendenza comunale ai Beni Comunali degli edifici monumentali e delle catacombe all'interno di Villa Torlonia," December 21st, 2000, 325,257.95 (approved); 230, b3.1.1.3, "Completamento indagini, progettazione ed avvio interventi a tutela e valorizzazione delle catacombe ebraiche all'interno di Villa Torlonia," December 21st, 2000, 258,228.45 (approved).

⁶⁹ Hirschfeld, 2008, pp. 35-36 and n. 74 and M. Ranieri Panetta, "Ecco le catacombe del Duce," *L'Espresso*, vol 45, 18-25, May 4th, 2000, p. 256. Barbera, 2003, p. 55, notes a lack of funds allocated to the site during preparations in Rome for the 2000 Jubilee, and, on pp. 55-56, explains that the work of the Soprintendenza Archeologica di Roma is complicated by the multiple city and state entities responsible for the Villa Torlonia, a site that contains diverse types of monuments in urgent need of conservation, including botanical features. In addition, there is a serious lack of prior documentation of the area, especially of other subterranean features below the villa grounds (Barbera, 2003, pp. 59-60). Magnani Cianetti, 2003, p. 58, raises the need to trace the sources of continued "stresses" on the structure from the villa overhead, a study that, in 2003, lacked necessary funding to extend beyond a "diagnostic" stage. At present, some steps have been taken to coordinate the cultivation of the villa grounds and prevent any building for commercial use, keeping it an entirely pedestrian zone (Barbera, 2003, p. 64).

The regular opening of the Torlonia catacombs to the public has been put on hold many times while research on the site continues to be carried out by scholars from Italy and abroad.⁷⁰ Plans for a “Museo della Shoah”, or Holocaust Museum, designed by the architects Luca Zevi and Giorgio Maria Tamburini, now propose access to the Jewish catacombs from a new complex on the via Alessandro Torlonia, a sort of “black box” inscribed with the names of circa 2,000 Jewish victims of the Holocaust from Italy.⁷¹

From recent studies of atmospheric conditions inside the catacombs, as well more general concerns about site safety, it is difficult to say whether or not this particular detail will ever be realized, or if the catacombs themselves will soon be open to the public on a greater scale.⁷² At this time, Rome’s vast ambitions for the Villa Torlonia may finally provide the answer.

Figure 7. Proposal for Rome’s Holocaust Museum showing the location of the catacombs below the villa grounds. G. Cuccia, *Roma - Via Nomentana. Da passeggiata dei papi a grande arteria urbana*, Rome, 2007, p. 62, fig. 6.20.

⁷⁰ Based on the results of microclimate studies, including samples of microfunghi and bacteria, as well as measurements of noxious gasses present in the site, the Soprintendenza Archeologica di Roma does not advocate the daily admittance of large numbers of people, and recommends, instead, tight control over group numbers and the length of each stay inside the site (Barbera, 2003, p. 63). The lighting necessary for public visits would also increase the growth of organisms on many surface areas of the catacomb (Barbera, 2003, p. 60).

⁷¹ Curcia, 2007, pp. 62-63.

⁷² Magnani Cianetti, 2003, p. 57, believes that the collapse of certain areas of the catacomb is not due to widespread structural problems, but rather from individual issues such as the position of a certain gallery, or a weakness of a small geological area at a certain point. The intense presence of loculi in some areas can also cause a wall to collapse, as well as the flat roofs of many of the corridors, which have gradually taken on an arch-like curve. The most frequent reason the Soprintendenza Archeologica di Roma has given in recent years for the Torlonia catacomb’s prolonged closure is the presence of noxious gasses in the galleries. In 2003, Barbera verified that high levels of radon had been detected in a number of areas (most often at the terminal points of galleries or other irregular areas of the excavation, like the interior of cubicula), creating a real “danger” to custodians and visitors (2003, p. 62). High levels of carbon dioxide were also present in the galleries. These gasses had accumulated in the catacombs at the time all access points were sealed into the site. Yet a simple “airing out” by re-opening the closed airshafts was feared to considerably alter the climactic conditions inside the site with inevitable damage to its paintings (Barbera, 2003, p. 63). When work began on the catacomb frescoes in 2003, only the skylight in front of the arcosolium A6 in the upper catacomb remained open although with modern reinforcements blocking access to A7 (Cappelletti, 2006, p. 165 & p. 168). G. Ciotoli et al., “Indoor Air Quality in an Archaeological Site: the Villa Torlonia Jewish Catacombs,” poster for *Geoitalia 2007*, finds that, so far, the microclimate inside the catacomb has not been negatively affected by these changes to reduce excess gas in the site, and a permanent radon monitoring system should now be installed to track any lingering effects.

Figure 8. Sarcophagus (fig. 2) in G. B. de Rossi, Ms. ICUR, 41, n. 16216.

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